

Integration of matter and wave

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What looks physically incompatible concept of wave and particle was integrated into a general wave of the complex energy. With the constant energy of a momentum factor and a mass factor, the state of energy is determined by the value of momentum and mass. In general, the energy is separated into the complex value with the imaginary mass and real momentum, from which the wave is derived by plugging the complex energy into the wavefunction of plane wave. As a result, a general expression of the matter, wave and matter wave is presented, which explains the role of imaginary mass in the propagation of energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The study has started to understand a matter and wave: how these two opposite physical properties can exist together in nature. Mass-energy equivalence was demonstrated more than a hundred years ago, in which the energy is expressed by the mass and momentum.

There is no suspicion about $E^2 = (mc^2)^2 + (pc)^2$, and it is accepted as usual as the energy of mass and momentum, by which the energy is supposed to increase by the speed of mass, and the tremendous energy will come out by the small amount of mass. From this point of view, the mass is considered to be a physical quantity that comes with the mysterious interaction with the field, which brings a illusion of the measurable mass and momentum, and it gives rise to the misunderstanding of the nature.

II. INTEGRATION OF MATTER AND WAVE

From my standpoint, the mass and momentum are not the physical quantities, but these are physical factors to characterize the behavior of energy, by which the motion of energy is determined. From the mass-energy equation, there is no information how it moves in the space and time, but it just describes magnitude of the energy by the mass and momentum with the critical constant c , nothing more than that. We are not able to know how this energy behaves in the space and time.

On the other hand, there is no information of the quantity, how much energy moves in the space and time from Maxwell's equation that is derived by interweaving the electric and magnetic fields. However, it allows us to see the motion of the wave through the space and time, which is equivalent to the motion of energy, not only for the light wave. The constant energy is expressed by $E_n^2 = (p_n c)^2 + (m_n c^2)^2$ [1] with

$$p_n c = \frac{v_n}{c} E_n \quad \text{and} \quad m_n c^2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} E_n, \quad (1)$$

FIG. 1. With a constant total energy, the massive energy decreases by $\frac{1}{\gamma}$, while the massless energy increases by $\frac{v}{c}$.

where the speed v_n is not the speed of mass either, and thus it is not about the particle, but is of the energy. With the constant total energy E_n , the massive energy varies in reverse to the massless energy of the momentum p_n , and then it gives the same expression of the original equation.

A measurable quantity, m_n and p_n are not just physical quantities, but are factors that define the motion of the energy in the space and time, which come into play in the wave equation $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = v^2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$. The mass m_n confines the motion of the energy in the time, and the wave is attenuated by $e^{-\frac{1}{m_n c^2 t}}$, whereas the momentum p_n play a role of dissipating the energy into the space. By plugging the energy of $E_n = p_n c + i m_n c^2$ and $E_n^* = p_n c - i m_n c^2$ into the wavefunction, the motion of wave is determined by $e^{i \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct)}$ and $e^{-i \frac{1}{\hbar} p_n (x - ct)}$, by which the energy goes to propagate. According to this, the mass and momentum work as physical factors as describing how the energy interact with the space and time, which determines the state of energy as well, and the matter and wave are integrated as a simple words as shown below.

1. $m_n \neq 0$ & $p_n = 0 \rightarrow$ Mass state
2. $m_n = 0$ & $p_n \neq 0 \rightarrow$ Wave state
3. $m_n \neq 0$ & $p_n \neq 0 \rightarrow$ Matter wave state

In other words, the speed of energy changes corresponding to the massless and massive energies, and the energy takes a different state that is switched depending on the values of p_n and m_n . It implies that the momentum and mass determine the state of energy, by which

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FIG. 2. Energy of $E_n^2 = (p_n c)^2 + (m_n c^2)^2$ is separated into a complex form of E_n and E_n^* that are delivered by the wavefunctions ψ_n^* and ψ_n .

the energy appears to be a mass, wave or in between both states, in which the matter and wave exist together without violating each other. For the energy of $p_n = 0$, it becomes stationary, while the speed of energy goes to c for the energy of $m_n = 0$. An interesting state comes from the state of $p_n \neq 0$ and $m_n \neq 0$, in which the energy has both the massless and massive energies, and the speed of energy appears to be $0 < v_n < c$. It gives rise to the nature of the wave and particle and its mixed state that appears by the duality.

It tells that the energy moves in parallel paths by wavefunctions of ψ_n and ψ_n^* , corresponding to each complex energy since the energy is separated into E and E^* as shown in Fig.2, which implies that the energy, whatever it is, is not able to be delivered by squared form of E^2 , but it is supposed to move by the complex form, which is delivered separately by the corresponding wave.

In the figure 2, a wave phase of θ_n and θ_n^* are assigned for each energy conjugate of E_n and E_n^* by $\theta_n = k_n x - \omega_n t = \frac{1}{\hbar}(p_n x - E_n t)$ and $\theta_n^* = k_n^* x - \omega_n^* t = \frac{1}{\hbar}(p_n^* x - E_n^* t) = \frac{1}{\hbar}(p_n x - E_n^* t)$ since $p_n^* = p_n$. By plugging E_n and E_n^* into the wavefunctions of ψ_n and ψ_n^* , it becomes as follows, ignoring the amplitude,

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_n &= e^{i\theta_n} = e^{i\frac{1}{\hbar}\{p_n x - (p_n c - im_n c^2)t\}} \\ &= e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_n c^2 t} e^{i\frac{1}{\hbar}p_n(x-ct)} \\ \psi_n^* &= e^{-i\theta_n} = e^{-i\frac{1}{\hbar}\{p_n x - (p_n c + im_n c^2)t\}} \\ &= e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_n c^2 t} e^{-i\frac{1}{\hbar}p_n(x-ct)},\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

which is the general expression of the wavefunctions that emerges from the complex energy of mass m_n with a momentum p_n , and the wave phase becomes $\theta_n = \frac{1}{\hbar}p_n(x-ct) = \frac{1}{\hbar}(p_n x - p_n c t) = k_n x - \omega_n t$, which is consistent with the wave phase of the conventional plane wave that is described by a angular wave number k_n and angular frequency ω_n , without a mass. From the equation 1, the momentum and mass become as follows:

$$\frac{m_n^2}{p_n^2} = \frac{1}{v_n^2} - \frac{1}{c^2}, \quad (3)$$

in which the speed of energy is supposed to change, while the speed of wave remains the constant from the fact that the mass becomes an attenuating factor of $e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_n c^2 t}$ in

the time, which distinguishes the matter wave [3] from the plane wave, and it implies that the wave of $0 < m_n$ is heavier than the wave of $m_n = 0$, but moves at the same speed.

From the fact that the energy of $0 < m_n$ moves at $v_n < c$ with different n that enables the speed of wave equal to the speed of matter, a wavefunction ψ_n is supposed to be superposed by $\Psi = \sum_n \psi_n$ with $(n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$. In other words, the imaginary mass of m_n and real momentum p_n makes the speed of wave equal to the speed of matter by $\frac{dw_n}{dk_n} = \frac{dE_m}{dp_m}$, which agrees with that the speed of energy is equal to the speed of wave.

For $n = 0$ that is equivalent to the rest-mass, the energy appears $E_0^2 = (p_0 c)^2 + (m_0 c^2)^2 = (m_0 c^2)^2$ with $E_0 = im_0 c^2$ and $E_0^* = -im_0 c^2$, by which the wave becomes as follows:

$$\psi_0 = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2 t} e^{i\frac{1}{\hbar}p_0 x} \quad \text{and} \quad \psi_0^* = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2 t} e^{-i\frac{1}{\hbar}p_0 x}, \quad (4)$$

and there is no propagation of energy through the space. It brings the rest-energy of $E_0^2 = (m_0 c^2)^2$ to emerge from the rest-mass of m_0 , and becomes $E_0^* E_0 = (-im_0 c^2)(im_0 c^2) = (m_0 c^2)^2 = |E|^2 = (\hbar\omega_0)^2$ [2], which gives $\hbar\omega_0 = \pm m_0 c^2$ and $\omega_0 = \pm \frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2$. It indicates that the wave of the rest-mass has a both positive and negative angular frequencies, which implies that there are two waves of a rest-mass with a angular momentum that rotates in the opposite direction to each other in the complex domain.

From the equation 2, there are two cases possible with the wave of complex energy. The first case comes from the wave superposition with the same polarity such as $\Psi = \sum_n \psi_n \rightarrow \psi_0 = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2 t}$ and of $\Psi^* = \sum_n \psi_n^* \rightarrow \psi_0^* = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2 t}$, and it becomes a matter with a charge. The next one appears to be a radiation as expressed by $\sum(\psi_n + \psi_n^*) = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar}m_0 c^2 t} 2\cos\frac{1}{\hbar}p_0(x-ct) \rightarrow 2\cos\frac{1}{\hbar}p_c(x-ct)$ by the loss of mass m_0 , which is a mass-energy extraction, where a subscript c stands for the massless wave.

III. COUPLING STATE OF MATTER WAVE

From the fact that wavefunctions of ψ and ψ^* are obtained by substituting the complex relativistic energy into the plane wave, it is obvious that the wave of $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$ is valid both for the matter and wave regardless of the presence of the mass and the momentum. Up to here, the complex energy is supposed to be in the same place, which means that the distance between conjugate energies is zero, not separated by the space.

In order to understand the matter and wave, it is necessary to investigate the wavefunctions ψ and ψ^* that are separated by the space, in which a wave of $0 < n < \infty$ has both properties of matter and wave. In the equation 2, conjugate wavefunctions of ψ_n and ψ_n^* are supposed to move through the space in the form of $\psi_n + \psi_n^*$. Denoted by ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- instead of ψ_n and ψ_n^* for a convenience, wavefunctions of ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- that are separated by the

FIG. 3. The positive wavefunction ψ_n^+ is coupled with the negative wavefunction ψ_n^- as appearing to be a wave of $\psi_n^+ + \psi_n^-$ in between.

space can be coupled by a wave $\psi_n^+ + \psi_n^-$, and then this coupling wave appears to be stationary: one is moving forward and the other is going backward in between.

The coupling wave is not affected by exchanging the position of E_n^+ and E_n^- as long as the displacement of Δx is not changed, and thus substituting $x - \frac{\Delta x}{2}$ and $x + \frac{\Delta x}{2}$ into ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- is identical to plugging $x + \frac{\Delta x}{2}$ and $x - \frac{\Delta x}{2}$ into ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- . As a result, the wave of $\psi_n^+ + \psi_n^-$ of the complex energies E_n^+ and E_n^- that is separated by Δx can be expressed by $2A_n \cos k_n(x - ct)(\cos \frac{\Delta x}{2} k_n + i \sin \frac{\Delta x}{2} k_n)$ as well as $2A_n \cos k_n(x - ct)(\cos \frac{\Delta x}{2} k_n - i \sin \frac{\Delta x}{2} k_n)$ with $A_n = e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t}$ and $\frac{1}{\hbar} p_n = k_n$. By adding these two waves and divide it by 2, it becomes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_n^+ + \psi_n^- &= 2e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t} \cos k_n(x - ct) \cos k_n \frac{\Delta x}{2} \\ &= 2e^{-\frac{1}{\hbar} m_n c^2 t} \cos k_n(x - ct) \cos k_n \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} \pi, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\cos k_n \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda} \pi$ is a coupling factor that varies depending on the distance between the complex energies, and it confines the wave to stay in between E_n^+ and E_n^- . Thus, the wave between the complex energies that is separated by distance Δx appears to be a coupling state of wavefunctions of ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- .

For both energy conjugates, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are possible, and therefore there are a bunch of energies with

different n depending on the interference condition such as a $n\lambda = 2\pi r$, by which a wave superposition of each ψ_n^+ and ψ_n^- is possible. As a result, it brings a particle-like wave superposition with the speed of $\frac{dE}{dp}$ without a rest-mass.

With the energy conjugates that is separated by the distance, there is an additional factor that comes into play a role of coupling the energy conjugates. With the distance of $\Delta x = 0$, it becomes a wave that is confined by the mass, and it is released as a massless wave when the mass disappears, which comes out to be a light wave.

IV. SUMMARY

A complex wave was derived by substituting the complex energy of modified mass-energy equation into the plane wave. With a complex energy of E_n and E_n^* , the wave is supposed to propagate through the spacetime that is attenuated due to the massive factor m_n in the time, which makes the wave stay in the space. A wave was divided into three different states depending on the value of the momentum p_n and mass m_n of the squared energy E^2 , which determines the behavior of the energy and how it appears in the space and time, whether a matter, a wave or a dual state in between. With $0 < p_n$ and $0 < m_n$, the wave comes to be a heavy wave that is supposed to be superposed, which is distinguished from the massless wave of $m_n = 0$. A matter and wave are explained by the general description, in which conjugate wavefunctions are separated by the space and are connected by the coupling factor of the distance that makes the wave stationary in between. To be a final statement, it implies that the energy consists of two components of the mass m_n and momentum p_n , by which m_n plays a role of the binding factor of the massless energy of p_n , and then it propagates as a form of wave by interacting with the space and time.

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[2] L. de Broglie, *Non-Linear Wave Mechanics* (Elsevier, 1960).

[3] L. Okun, *Energy and mass in relativity theory* (World Scientific, 2009).